

Impact of Emotional Intelligence on Academic Achievement Among High School Students in Nagaland

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Several studies in India and abroad have explored the link between emotional intelligence and academic achievements among adolescents. While most have reported significant associations, a few disagreed. Nagaland shows poor academic levels and deteriorating standards which could be attributed to low emotional intelligence despite rich culture. Hardly any studies published. This paper presents data from a major research done during 2019 among high school students in Nagaland determining the impact of emotional intelligence on academic achievements. Emotional intelligence was low but correlated significantly with academic performance based on a random sample survey of 911 adolescents, both boys and girls, in 9th and 10th grades from government and private schools using validated measuring tools and in depth qualitative studies. Findings comparing with similar studies done elsewhere reveal an urgent need for education and counseling of students, teachers and parents on emotional intelligence and how it could be enhanced to improve academic performances.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Academic achievement, Motivation, Adolescents, Nagaland

Introduction

Daniel Goleman bestselling book, *Emotional Intelligence: Why it can matter more than I.Q.* (Goleman, 1995) provoked serious discussion on the crucial role emotional intelligence in academic prowess especially during adolescence and among high school students (Bar On, 2010). Originally coined by two psychologists, John D. Mayer and Peter Salovey who through a series of academic writings during 1993 and 1995 refined the definition of emotional intelligence as “the ability to recognize emotions, to access and use emotions to help support cognitive processes, to understand emotions and emotional knowledge, and to handle or regulate emotions in order to promote emotional and intellectual development.” (Mayer & Salovey, 1990, 1997). Several studies were done among College and University students both in India and abroad (Soni et al 2019; Wijekoon et al 2017; Samari and Tasmabi, 2006; Joibari et al 2011;

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Ameneh et al 2015) linking emotional intelligence with academic achievement and work performance. Similar research among high school students (Bharwad, 2015; Preeti, 2013; Shruti and Vijaya, 2010; Velmurugan and Balakrishnan, 2013; Yahaya et al 2011; Maharishi and Parameswari 2013) showed varied results but generally confirming that emotional intelligence does influence better academic outcomes.

There is scarcely any published studies done among indigenous populations such as in Nagaland and other northeastern states of India, who suffer from poor socioeconomic and educational facilities and show poor academic performances. Except for a small study on tribals (Sagtam and Talwar, 2013) the emotional intelligence levels of Nagaland adolescents and the impact on academic achievements is not known.

Nagaland is one of the hill states in the North- East, famous for its rich mosaic of numerous tribes with their rich culture (Devi, 2010). The total population of Nagaland is 1,980,602, person (Census of India, 2011) and density of population is 119 per sq.km. The state is predominantly rural with 82.26% of population living in villages. The State Council of Educational Research and Training (SCERT) Nagaland reported that with the implementation of Non-detention policy (NDP) in Nagaland, in 2011 the state witnessed a staggering indication of deteriorating education. (Shukla and Zetsuyi, 2006) In 2013, 35000 students appeared in class-IX out of which 15,000 failed. In 2014, 4000 students in class-IX were dropped out of school.(Nagaland Post, 2016; New Indian Express, 2018). Teachers and school administrators believe that students have developed a “lackadaisical” attitude towards their study leading to huge dropout rates. Further while the quantity of students is increasing, quality has become the biggest casualty. It is killing the future of the students as stated by the Naga Students’ Federation.

Till 1878, prior to the advent of the American missionaries in Nagaland, education was imparted by the family, community and Morung institution through informal indigenous modes.(Devi 2010) It was operative at all stage of human life. Indigenous system of education can be seen into two institutions rather through two social institutions viz; i) The Family and ii) The Morung i.e. dormitories for boys and girls is one of the most important features of the social structure of the Nagas in the Institution of the Morung. It is common to all the Nagas but its working differed from tribe to tribe, with main general objectives of education in all forms. Development of proper habits manners, and character in educational, social and religious contexts were the main features of the Morung. The beginning of formal education can be traced way back to 19th century (Chasie, 2004). Despite such rich background , it is inferred that the Emotional Intelligence of High school. Students may be low and responsible for rise in school dropout rates, lack of student motivation, poor study habits, poor academic achievement. Poor Emotional Intelligence may be also leading to low Motivation, which is the key to academic success. Before drawing form conclusions and planning for the future, the first step is to estimate the levels of emotional Intelligence among Nagaland high school students and determine if low emotional score leads to poor academic performances. Hence this research undertaken as part of the doctoral dissertation of the first author.

Material and Methods

A mixed method research design was adopted. The studies were approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee of Martin Luther Christian University, Shillong. The quantitative part consisted of a Cross-sectional study of an adequate number of adolescents studying in grades 9 and 10 from representative random cluster sample of schools using a specially prepared self-administered questionnaire. Additional data on academic performances for two years were obtained from the school administration. The qualitative study was based on Focus Group Discussions on purposive samples of teachers, parents and students as well as on selective Case reports designed to illustrate the role of socio-cultural and demographic/environmental factors underlying the relationships among the emotional intelligence, external and internal motivational factors and academic performances. The findings from all these sources were used to prepare a draft school counselling program that was then circulated and discussed with experts and stakeholders, mainly parents, teachers, school administrators and a sample of high school students before finalizing.

The research was conducted in the Kohima District of Nagaland, which is divided into eight (8) Administrative Blocks as depicted in figure I.

Figure I: Kohima District Administrative Map

The eight blocks are: Botsa, Chiephobozou, Jakhama, Kezocha, Kohima Sardar, Sechü (Zubza), Tseminyu and Tsogin. The circled highlighted areas in the map figure represent the places where the researcher carried out the study under each block.

Quantitative Surveys

Both government and private schools having classes till class ten(X) were taken for selection of the study and those who has classes only up to eighth grade were excluded. Applying the stratified random sampling method, 14 schools were randomly selected after applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Based on earlier experiences, it is assumed that at least 25 to 30 percent of the children in these age groups would have low emotional intelligence (EI), i.e a score of 20 or less. Taking type 1 error as 5%, power of 80%, and precision as 20% of the presumed estimate, the minimum sample size was estimated to be around 800 to 900. Permission was obtained from the District Education Officer (DE.O) to conduct research from the selected schools, after which a letter from researcher and the permission letter from the DEO was given to each selected school seeking permission to conduct the study in their school. After permission was granted by the concerned school principal and authorities, appointment was made to conduct the study. The researcher then visited each school personally and administered the questionnaires:

1. “Emotional Intelligence scale” The questionnaire consists of a total 31 questions, where the respondents have to score in the given two options, tick ‘Yes’ or “No”. The questions were based on understanding emotions, understanding motivation, empathy and handling relations. The scale is meant for the use from 12 years and above.(Singh and Narain,2014)
2. “Academic Self- Regulation Questionnaire (SRQ-A)” The questionnaire consists of 32 questions; the questionnaire is a likert 4 point scale of Very True; Sort of True; Not Very True; and Not At All respectively where the respondents have to tick the relevant options. Therefore the higher the score the higher the regulatory style; the questionnaire uses four subscale: External Regulation, Introjected Regulation, Identified Regulation and Intrinsic Motivation. According to the SRQ-A introjection refer to taking in a regulation but not accepting it as one’s own; identification refers to accepting the value of the activity as personally important and integration refers to integrating that identification with other aspects of one’s self. External & introjected regulations are considered relatively controlled forms of extrinsic motivation, whereas identified and integrated regulations are considered relatively autonomous or intrinsic (Ryan and Desi, 2000).
3. To measure the Academic Achievement, the researcher collected on the two years consecutive academic grades of each individual respondent.

After formal introductions detailed information was given on the purpose of visit, the study and the questionnaires. Subsequently a consent form was handed out to the students seeking their participation and assuring them of confidentiality and security of the data. For smooth administration of the questionnaire clear instructions were given and requested the respondents to read the instructions carefully and if there is any confusion, the researcher made sure to clarify their doubts. There was no fixed time limit; however it took about 40 to 45 minutes in its completion.

The consistency (precision) and the validity (accuracy) of the tools were carried out in a school on 20 students which did participate in the study. The pilot study

helped in understanding the content of the questionnaire, whether the tools will be applicable in the concerned study area as the questionnaire adopted were standardized in nature, whether the questions were clear and applicable to the students keeping in mind the background of the students and the objectives of the research. After the collection of the data, the researcher, following the scoring procedure of the manual of the questionnaire of Emotional Intelligence scale, the scale was divided into four dimensions (Understanding emotions, understanding motivation, empathy, and handling relations) where the items were again classified into positive and negative. The answers of those items which tallied with the answers given in the scoring key were given a score+1. If they didn't tally, they were given a score of zero. The obtained final score on Emotional Intelligence Scale was interpreted as:

Range of score	Interpretation
20 or less	Low Emotional Intelligence
21 to 26	Average Emotional Intelligence
27 and above	High Emotional Intelligence

For scoring the SRQ-A (standard version), first the researcher calculated the subscale for each of the four subscale by averaging the items that make up the subscale. Very true is scored 4; sort of true 3; not very true 2; not at all true 1. The Self Regulatory style can be used in three different types of analysis. The researcher for this study applied the method of analyzing each subscale score separately of each individual participant for each style. Then the researcher formed a score for controlled regulation by averaging across external and introjected items which make the extrinsic motivation, and a score for autonomous regulation or intrinsic motivation by averaging across identified, integrated regulation by averaging across identified, integrated and/or intrinsic items. The researcher by doing so was able to find the level of which motivation is mostly present in the respondents that is whether it's intrinsic or extrinsic motivation.

For scoring the academic achievement, the researcher first of all entered all the grades of two years of each individual respondent into excel sheet, and scored the total of each year separately using the Nagaland Board of School Education formula of scoring the grades which was categorized into nine (9) dimensions; of the students. After which both the percentage were averaged and the nine dimensions were further categorized into four category.

Range of score	Grades	Interpretation
81-100	A1 –A2	Excellent
61-80	B1-B2	Good
41-60	C1-C2	Fair
40 and below	D, E1 & E2	Poor

Qualitative Studies

Focus Group Discussions(FGD)

Three focus group discussions (FGD) were conducted with 15 participants who are the representatives of the sample which the researcher is concerned about to explore their views and opinions. The FGDs were held separately for the three distinct groups: parents (of the students surveyed, young parents, elderly parents, male parent, female parent, different profession and income, different family environment), teachers (government, private, three years and above teaching experience, male teacher, female teacher), students (both male and female students, both government and private school students, different family background) to obtain views and opinions and information of each category's specific needs. The researcher was the chief facilitator, with assistants. The group's composition and the group discussion were carefully planned to create a nonthreatening environment in which the participants were free to talk openly. Members were actively encouraged to express their opinions. The entire process was tape-recorded with their permission and consent.

Case Studies

Four case studies were conducted purposively identifying 2 students who had achieved the highest score in the measurement of Emotional Intelligence test and 2, who have scored the lowest. It was hoped that the comparative analyses of the case studies of the Four distinct participants would provide the clues for facilitating and constraining factors in the development of emotional intelligence. The students were contacted individually and their consent obtained for the interview ensuring strict confidentiality and security of the information to be used exclusively for the research project. A suitable place and time was chosen according to the convenience of the respondent with no disturbances or distractions. A special interview schedule was developed and adequate notes taken during the interview. All data were edited for completion, corrected and entered onto Microsoft excel sheets for data management and analysed using SPSS software.

Findings

For the quantitative study, a representative random cluster sample of 911 adolescent children were studied, 366 from Government schools and 545 from Private schools. There were 853 tribal children and only 58 non tribal. The ages varied from 13 to 19 years. Approximately half were females. 594 were in the 9th grade and the rest in 10th. The similarity of the children between the two types of schools in terms of gender is examined in Table 1, by class in Table 2, by tribe in Table 3 and by Age in Table 4.

Gender	Government		Private		Total	
	No.	Percentage	No.	Percentage	No.	Percentage
Female	166	45.4	278	51.0	444	48.7
Male	200	54.6	267	49.0	467	51.3
Total	366	100.0	545	100.0	911	100.0

The distribution of class was not statistically significant by the two types of school as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Distribution of class by the two type of school

Class	Types of school					
	Government		Private		Total	
	No.	Percentage	No.	Percentage	No.	Percentage
Class10	109	29.8	208	38.2	317	34.8
Class 9	257	70.2	337	61.8	594	65.2
Total	366	100.0	545	100.0	911	100.0

The distribution of tribal's and non tribal was not statistically significant between the two types of school as presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Distribution of Tribal and Non-Tribal Children by type of School

Table 1: Distribution of Gender by type of School						
	Government		Private		Total	
	No.	Percentage	No.	Percentage	No.	Percentage
Non Tribal	166	45.4	278	51.0	444	48.7
Tribal	200	54.6	267	49.0	467	51.3
Total	366	100.0	545	100.0	911	100.0

The distribution of age is not statistically significant by types of school as displayed in Table 4.

Table 4: Distribution of age by type of School

Age (Years)	Type of School			
	Government		Private	
	No.	Percent	No.	Percent
13	2	0.5	6	1.1
14	53	14.5	89	16.3
15	101	27.6	159	29.2
16	102	27.9	154	28.3
17	70	19.1	91	16.7
18	34	9.3	34	6.2
19	4	1.1	12	2.2
Total	366	100.0	545	100.0
MEAN (yrs)	15.83		15.1	
SD (yrs)	1.24		1.2	

There were no statistically significant differences among the children by their gender in terms of class of study, tribe, type of school and age.

Academic Achievement

There were no significant differences between the two years and the mean (SD) marks was 45.1(12.8), ranging from about 12 to 95. The assessments based on two years 2016 and 2017 were averaged and the descriptive statistics are given in Table 5.

Table 5: Academic Achievement (AA) of all 911 students (percentage)

Academic Achievement	No.	Mean	SE	Median	SD	Range	Minimum	Maximum
2016	911	49.2	0.49	49.0	14.72	85.0	11..0	96..0
2017	911	40.9	0.45	40.0	13.46	81..0	12..0	93..0
Average	911	45.1	0.43	43.5	12.83	83..0	11..5	94..5

There were no statistically significant differences in the different subgroups by type of school, by class or tribe or by gender.

The average Academic Achievement of students were further graded into four different groups such as; Excellent 81-100, Good 61-80 ,Fair 41-60 and Poor 40 or below .The findings for all 911 students are as displayed in Table 6.

Table 6: Category of overall academic achievement (A.A) of all 911 students

Category of Academic Achievement	No.	Percent
Excellent	13	1.4
Good	97	10.6
Fair	456	50.1
Poor	345	37.9
Total	911	100.0

Thus only 1% is classified as Excellent while nearly 40% fared poorly. The findings by type of school or class or tribe or by gender showed no statistically significant differences.

Emotional Intelligence (E.I)

The descriptive statistics of the Emotional Intelligence for all the 911 students are presented in table 7.

Table 7: Emotional Intelligence (EI) of all 911 students

EI	No.	Mean	SE	Median	SD	Range	Min.	Max.
Total	911	19.88	.127	20.00	3.843	23	6	29

The EI ranged from 6 to 29 with a mean (SD) of 19.9(3.84). The distribution was fairly normal with the median and the mean having the same value. The EI by type of school or class or Tribe or by gender did not show any statistically significant differences.

The Emotional Intelligence Scale or total score were then interpreted into three different categories as; Low Emotional Intelligence (20 or less), Average Emotional Intelligence (21-26), and High Emotional Intelligence (27 and above), which is shown for all the 911 students in Table 8.

Table 8: Category of overall Emotional Intelligence of 911 Students

Category of Emotional Intelligence	No.	Percent
High	31	3.4
Average	354	38.9
Low	526	57.7
Total	911	100.0

It is appalling to note that nearly 60% have low Emotional Intelligence. The EI categories by type of school showed that the proportion with low EI was significantly higher among pupils of government schools as compared to those in private schools, 65%vs 52%, $p < 0.05$, but there were not by class, tribe or Academic Achievement. The Overall association of Emotional intelligence with Academic Achievement is shown in Table 9.

Table 9: Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement of all 911 students

Academic Achievement Category	Emotional Intelligence Category							
	High		Average		Low		Total	
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
Excellent	2	6.5	3	0.8	8	1.5	13	1.4
Good	5	16.1	63	17.8	29	5.5	97	10.6
Fair	19	61.3	197	55.6	240	45.6	456	50.1
Poor	5	16.1	91	25.7	249	47.3	345	37.9
Total	31	100.0	354	100.0	526	100.0	911	100.0
P – value	.000							

The Chi-square test was highly significant ($p < 0.001$) showing the impact of EI on AA. As noted from the table, only 16% of high EI were rated Poor as compared to 47% of Low EI. Likewise, nearly 23% with high EI were rated Good or Excellent AA as compared to only 7% among Low EI. These differences are also statistically highly significant ($p < 0.001$).

This relationship was examined in terms of various backgrounds of students and showed statistically significant associations regardless of type of school, class, tribe or gender.

This relationship was examined in terms of various backgrounds of students. The association in terms of type of school is shown in Table 10.

Table 10: Emotional intelligence and academic achievement by type of school

AA Categories	Emotional Intelligence Interpretation															
	Government								Private							
	High		Average		Low		Total		High		Average		Low		Total	
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
Excellent	0	0.0	1	0.8	5	2.1	6	1.6	2	8.0	2	0.9	3	1.0	7	1.3
Good	0	0.0	21	17.4	14	5.9	35	9.6	5	20.0	42	18.0	15	5.2	62	11.4
Fair	4	66.7	62	51.2	104	43.5	170	46.4	15	60.0	135	57.9	136	47.4	286	52.5
Poor	2	33.3	37	30.6	116	48.5	155	42.3	3	12.0	54	23.2	133	46.3	190	4.9
Total	6	100	121	100	239	100	366	100	25	100	233	100	287	100	545	100
P value	.002								.000							

Chi square test of association was highly significant in both types of schools, confirming the strong impact of EI and AA regardless of where the student is studying. The association by Gender is presented in Table 11.

Table 11: Emotional intelligence interpretation on academic achievement categories by gender

AA Categories	Emotional intelligence interpretation															
	Male								Female							
	High		Average		Low		Total		High		Average		Low		Total	
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
Excellent	1	7.7	1	0.5	5	1.9	7	1.5	1	5.6	2	1.2	3	1.2	6	1.4
Good	2	15.4	36	19.5	16	5.9	54	11.6	3	16.7	27	16.0	13	5.1	43	9.7
Fair	8	61.5	103	55.7	130	48.3	241	51.6	11	61.1	94	55.6	110	42.8	215	48.4
Poor	2	15.4	45	24.3	118	43.9	165	35.3	3	16.7	46	27.2	131	51.0	180	40.5
Total	13	100	185	100	269	100	467	100	18	100	169	100	257	100	444	100
P value	.000								.000							

Among both boys and girls, EI was strongly associated with AA as seen from the statistically significant Chi-square values ($p < 0.001$).

The Association by Tribe of student is presented in Table 12.

Table 12: Emotional intelligence interpretation on academic achievement categories by tribe

AA Categories	Emotional Intelligence Interpretation															
	Tribal's								Non tribal							
	High		Average		Low		Total		High		Average		Low		Total	
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
Excellent	2	6.7	3	0.9	6	1.2	11	1.3	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	5.6	2	3.4
Good	5	16.7	57	17.1	25	5.1	87	10.2	0	0.0	6	28.6	4	11.1	10	17.2
Fair	19	63.3	188	56.5	226	46.1	433	50.8	0	0.0	9	42.9	14	38.9	23	39.7
Poor	4	13.3	85	25.5	233	47.6	22	37.7	1	100.0	6	28.6	16	44.4	23	39.7
Total	30	100	333	100	490	100	853	100	1	100	21	100	36	100	58	100
P value	.000								.426							

While the chi square test was highly significant for the tribal's ($p < 0.001$) showing strong association of EI with AA, among Non-tribal, the association was not statistically significant ($P = 0.4$). Finally the association by class of study is displayed in Table 13.

Table 13: Emotional intelligence interpretation on academic achievement categories by class

AA Categories	Emotional Intelligence Interpretation															
	Class IX								Class X							
	High		Average		Low		Total		High		Average		Low		Total	
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
Excellent	2	9.5	2	0.9	7	2.0	11	1.9	0	0.0	1	0.7	1	0	2	0.6
Good	3	14.3	43	19.5	20	5.7	66	11.1	2	20.0	20	14.9	9	5.2	31	9.8
Fair	13	61.9	104	47.3	135	38.2	252	42.4	6	60.0	3	69.4	105	60.7	204	64.4
Poor	3	14.3	71	32.3	191	54.1	265	44.6	2	20.0	20	14.9	58	33.5	80	25.2
Total	21	100	220	100	33	100	594	100	10	100	134	100	173	100	317	100
P value	.000								.003							

The Overall Correlation between EI and AA was $r = 0.235$, $p < 0.001$ and the correlation coefficients in the various subgroups are presented in Table 14.

Table 14: Correlations between ei and aa for various subgroups

Category		Correlation Coefficient	p	number
By type of school	Government	0.222	<0.001	594
	Private	0.280	<0.001	317
By class of study	9	0.222	<0.001	594
	10	0.273	<0.001	317
By tribal and non tribal	Tribal	0.246	<0.001	863
	Non- Tribal	0.121	0.394	58
By gender	Female	0.273	<0.001	444
	Male	0.196	<0.001	467

Association of Emotional intelligence and Motivation, both extrinsic and intrinsic, is presented in Table 15.

Table 15: Overall categorized or interpretation of emotional intelligence and intrinsic and extrinsic motivation

Emotional Intelligence Interpretation	Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation				P-value
	Extrinsic Motivation		Intrinsic Motivation		
	No.	Percent	No.	Percent	
High	24	3.0	7	6.2	.126
Average	307	38.4	47	42.0	
Low	468	58.6	58	51.8	
Total	799	100.0	112	100.0	

The P-Value is .125997. The result is not significant at $p < .05$.

Association of Academic Achievement with both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation is given in Table 16.

Table 16: Overall categorized association between academic achievement and intrinsic and extrinsic motivation

Academic Achievement Interpretation	Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation				P - value
	Extrinsic Motivation		Intrinsic Motivation		
	No.	Percent	No.	Percent	
Excellent	9	1.1	4	3.6	.016
Good	78	9.8	19	17.0	
Fair	408	51.1	48	42.9	
Poor	304	38.0	41	36.6	
Total	799	100.0	112	100.0	

The P-Value is .016383. The result is significant at $p < .05$.

We now present the findings from the various qualitative researches.

Qualitative Research: Focus Group Discussions (FDG)

Students FGD: The Group comprised of 4 male and 3 female students from different institutions, different classes, and different family environment. All were eager and enthusiastically participated in the discussion. 1) initially, the participants were ignorant about E.I but after a brief explanation, the group discussed the importance of E.I for school students as it helps in the overall performance and development of an individual. 2).The students discussed the importance of active participation on extracurricular activities and more participation and initiation from the school and administration. The students also argued on the mismanagement of time. 3) Discussed the role of teachers and the school on the development of E.I. and how creating an awareness for all the teachers, students, and the school authorities for a better understanding. 4) talking of the cultural contribution in the development of E.I, the students had mixed response some argued that Naga culture in general is not so helpful due to cultural restrictions to talk, share and express their views and opinions. Some of the participants were against the view as participation in cultural activities and listening to elders and peer relationship helped them. However both argued the need of a change and awareness. 5) Discussing on the role of parenting style and family environment on the development of E.I, there was mixed response but argued a need of change in the role of parents in today's society.

The discussion came to consensus that there is a need of awareness of E.I for students, parents, teachers and school, a need of change in the practise of cultural regulations and should be open to new positive change and adaptations. Importance should be given to parenting style, as well as E.I to be made aware at the school level, society, parents, teachers and the students through awareness programmes, workshops as it will create a better understanding, relationships and positive development. Importance of a role of a professional Counsellor at school and its role in building

the development of emotional growth academic, social, family relationships.

Teachers FGD: The group consists of 3 female teachers and 2 male teachers from government and private school, different years of experience in teaching, and school environment. 1.) At first the participants were ignorant about E.I but after a brief explanation, there was unanimity in agreeing that EI was very important and neglected in their children education as well as themselves. 2.) Discussed the role of importance of E.I for students and how it will determine the achievement or excel in their academic and personal self. Importance of awareness for teachers, parents and students was further discussed 3.) Role of contribution by extracurricular activities argued to have both positive and negative outcomes, some are of the view that extracurricular should be encouraged but also argued the importance of disturbances in their academic and therefore time management be given importance. However the group argued that extracurricular helps in building E.I. 4.) The teachers debated the role of teachers and administration on the development of E.I in students through their experiences and by taking initiatives in making changes and creating approachable environment and understand the students. The teachers also argued on the role of parents in developing EI in their children, that the parents and home environment are equally important with the role of the teachers, hence encouraged the awareness programmes and sensitization on E.I and role of parents. Some are of the opinion that with the current changing education system is helping in the development of the students 5.) Debating on the role of contribution by cultural factors, and the society, there was a mixed response as some of the members argued that the cultural values and participation is helping in the development such as society programmes, peer relationships, social activities, church engagement and family engagement. However some are of the view that not much positive contribution from the society and the cultural practices as it is more conservative and lack of freedom of expression.

The discussion came to consensus that there is a need of awareness of E.I for all the students, teachers, and parents. School environment, family environment and societal contribution to be focused on positive development, motivate the students and create new opportunities. Need for a change in the students overall development based curriculum and need of school counselling program. E.I in the school for the development of emotional stability and development of the students.

Parents FGD: The Group comprised of 3 fathers and 3 mothers from a variety of backgrounds. All were literate and cooperative in enthusiastically participating in the discussion. The salient features of the discussion are : (1) While initially there was ignorance on what EI was, but after explaining, there was unanimity in agreeing that EI was very important and neglected in their children's education(2) The parents debated on the role of parents in developing EI in their children, and through examples and incidents in their own life ,they illustrated the weaknesses in allowing children to express freely and instead banning any talk or opinions of the children in front of adults. Most parents seem strict on this not allowing children freedom to talk but agreed that they must become more liberal and sensitive to children's development

of emotional intelligence(3) Most parents were in favour of further education of parents and teachers on EI, as it seemed a new concept but they agreed it was important , and the parents must take a greater role(4) There was discussion on how Naga culture might influence the lifestyle of families and parents but there was no agreement on how culture can influence the present day life style as most are not aware of how parents lived and behaved in olden days and how the current families are losing the valuable lessons of earlier generations. However, it was generally agreed that culture and identity are important and play a major role in developing EI. Therefore again the curriculum must include these aspects in education.

In summary, the discussions were cordial and arrived at a consensus that EI was very important, must be developed through extracurricular and other programs in the school, that parents must also be educated and counselled on how to develop EI through changes in their parenting styles.

Case Studies

The highlights and summaries of the 4 case studies emphasized the following: The high scoring participants regardless of the differences in their socioeconomic status, ethnicity, parent's educational differences and family environment, the parents encourages and are supportive. One participant mentioned "We have a strong family relationship, I am open and free with my parents and siblings, and though my parents are strict at times my family is supportive" the client also say that "my parents take us for family outings and trips, visit relatives and spend family time together" (Male/17). Another participant mentioned "I am closer with my mother. But my mother is strict as compared with her father. I have good relationship with both my siblings, we shares almost everything, help each other our studies examples doing homework, project works etc" (Female/16). The low scoring participant however mentions that though there is "mostly every night we our family will have a fight because my father comes home drunk" the client also said " We all don't talk much in our family like we do share things but I know we all don't have very good relationship"(Male/). Another client reported that "My father is always busy with his works, even in the village like meetings and other works. So when he comes home also we hardly get time to talk or sit together" and further added "I wish that I will be able to get time to have family time together and share things but both our parents are very busy"(Female/). Whereas a high scoring mentioned there is family support and motivate him in participation in competitions and social activities "My parents most of the time allows me to participate and encourages to take part in programmes and competition but there is restrictions if it is going to affect my studies" (male/17).

The studies highlighted a mixed response on the motivation received from the elder's, society, teachers and family. One of the clients reported by saying that he is disappointed in the way the surroundings treat the young ones, lack of motivation, acknowledgment, being judgemental lack of resources for a student and meaningful awareness or programmes for the young ones. The clients mentioned "Positive competition should be encouraged and appreciated. Open new doors for the young generations and not always stuck with the same olden days of practise" (Male/17)

another participant mentioned that “there is few encouragements, lack of motivation and appreciation and more of comparison from the elders, relatives, or others, leaders and even teachers and at times parents, which de motivates and lost interesting in doing things, not everyone but majority are very discouraging”(Female/16). Another response added “ some of my elders and neighbours are very good like they encourage and motivate us to do this and that, but most of the elders or even the teachers are like they will only give opportunity to good students, or those who are smart” (male) “In school and also in our community like people only praise those who are good in studies and good with other things” in response to it the participant also said that “some Teachers are helpful when faced with doubts”(Female/)When asked on the contribution of the society and the surroundings a participant responded “even if we share our difficulties with others also they won’t take seriously and sometimes they are very judgemental and gossip bad things about us. Like our neighbours and elders specially” another participant mentioned likewise “I think It will be good if the elders also try to understand us better and show or encourage us and motivate us instead of comparing us with others or being judgemental” further on in the discussion a participant therefore said “I don’t want to share anything even though I face problems I try to keep it with myself” one participant also added “Many a times I feel that people won’t understand me like I think I am the only who is suffering and there is no one to share my problems to or don’t want to share as people will be very judgemental and laugh at me. Even my teachers sometimes they are very judgemental”.

The case studies also discussed the importance of the peer relationships as the participants mentions that peer relationships has much more affect on the participant “I learn a lot from friends circle, be it social, problems or difficulties, we lean on each other help and motivate and encourage each other in times of personal issues, problems with studies, decision making and thus I have close relationship with some few good friends” another participant also said that “I have some few good friends whom I am very close with and does almost everything together like doing task together, sharing things and problems, helping each other in times difficulties etc. My friend’s helps in deciding things when I am confused and I also help my friends”. “Experiences with friends and family helped me in being aware of my emotions”.

The case studies brought out the report that encouragement and understanding from the elders, community and society should be emphasized, more awareness programmes should be encouraged for all the teachers, students, and parents as the client mentions “more awareness and programmes will be helpful for the students as well as for the parent and child relationships as well as for the teachers, because some are not understanding at all. Doing and learning such activities helps in development of us and motivates and encourages and teaches us a lot” another participant adds “ it will be helpful if such programmes are conducted time and again so we will be able to refresh our mind and learn about our emotional wellbeing and understand each other better. Participation in outdoor activities, programmes, family interactions and sharing their experiences helps me better in reflecting myself while answering the E.I”

Discussion

Intelligence quotient (IQ) has long been considered as the main factor of academic success and achievement, but some critics assert that intellectual abilities are overemphasized.. Goleman (1995) claims that only 20% of a person's success can be attributed to I.Q. This claim prompts many researchers and academicians to explore and identify other factors that contribute another 80% to a person's success. Petrides et al (2014), suggest that emotional intelligence is relevant to scholastic achievement and deviant behavior at school, especially for disadvantaged and vulnerable adolescents. Maraichelvi & Rajan, (2013) mentioned, learning requires a person-centered process for students' growth and development. When emotional intelligence skills are the focus of learning, students are building human development behaviours that are intricately related to the positive outcomes of achievement, goal achievement and personal well-being. The findings from this research indicate that although the level of the correlation coefficient was rather low($r=+0.235$), it was statistically highly significant($p<0.01$) as noted from Tables 9-13 . Similar research done elsewhere show positive correlations ;for example, Chamundeswari (2013) in India found emotional intelligence(EI) and academic achievement(AA) are positively correlated with each other and significant ($r=+0.25$, $p<0.01$). An African study by Ogundokun and Adeyamo (2010) showed a very high and significant correlation between A.A and E.I ($r=+0.736$, $p<0.05$). A study at Delhi, India, by Soni et al (2019) brings out the fact that there lies a moderate relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of students. Several other studies also reported positive relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement (Parker et al 2005; Nasir and Masur, 2010; Samari and Tahmasbi, 2007;). On the other hand, Lawrence et al (2013) show that there is no significant correlation between E.I and A.A ($r= 0.165$, $p<0.05$) among the high school students. Likewise, Vandervoort (2006), Barchard (2003) and Suleman et al(2019) conclude that the academic success of the students which is based on their scores is not related to their emotional intelligence. They, however, concede that EI increases the chance of success due to the improvement of the learning trend in addition to improving personal, interpersonal and social relationships. Obviously, such variations are expected in view of many extraneous factors and must be interpreted carefully. Overall, both theoretical and practical considerations generally support the view that directly or indirectly the emotional intelligence contributes to better academic performances and success in later life. Thus the agenda for educational development in Nagaland should include enhancement of emotional intelligence especially among adolescents and high school students.

Emotional Intelligence was very well defined by Salovey and Mayer (1990). Emotions matter in every phase of life and shape our personality because they directly gauge how one reacts in a situation. Several studies have suggested that people who are emotionally stable perform better than who are more intelligent. Goleman , (2013) defined emotions as “acute disturbances of the individual and avers that there lies a moderate relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of students. Emotional intelligence of students is influenced by the behaviors of their

teachers, friends and family atmosphere and includes Self-Awareness and Self-Monitoring are prerequisites for students to access traditional academic material presented in the classroom. Furthermore the current demands of society require additional skills in several areas of emotional awareness, if children have successful adult lives. From the results of this study, it would be reasonable to conclude that many of the components of emotional intelligence such as ability to regulate oneself, self-awareness and motivation are the domains that directly contribute to the academic success of the students. Furthermore the ability of social skills and empathy will indirectly assist in helping the students to seek out academic assistance from teachers, parents, peers and the environs.

Billions of students spend at least five hours or more a day at schools which provide an important place for children and adolescents to grow. The school environment provides a developmental context, not only for students' academic learning but also for the growth of their emotional well-being and psychosocial adaptation (Martin and Brown, 2008), their emotional intelligence (Stillman et al., 2018), and their resilience level (Gómez-Baya and Mendoza, 2018). With the mushrooming of schools with high-power advertising, and intensive educational competition choosing "the best school" for children poses a serious dilemma. Therefore, understanding the factors that might impact students' development and selecting a school that could best foster students growth is a meaningful decision. However, not every school places greater importance to noncognitive skills as compared to cognitive inputs. While national educational policies undergird the curriculum and evaluation methods, ultimately it is the interest and commitment of the school management to place great emphasis on overall development of the school children.. It is important to note in this research, that children in government schools fare better than those in private schools as far as emotional intelligence and motivations(Table 10)Could it be that the private schools put more pressure on academic performances rather than on noncognitive aspects such as empathy, self complacency which form important components of emotional intelligence?(Mayer and Salvoey, 1997) Or would the government schools promote more extracurricular activities such as sports and other leisure activities ? This needs further research as students need emotional intelligence (EI) for their better academic excellence. There are three important psychological dimensions of EI: Emotional sensitivity (ES), emotional maturity (EM) and emotional competency (EC), which motivate students to recognize truthfully, interpret honestly and handle tactfully the dynamics of their behavioral pattern.(Ganpat et al, 2018). The importance of extracurricular activities were brought out more forcefully in the Focus Group Discussions of both students and teachers The low EI scores and poor academic achievements noted in this research (Tables 9-13)do not speak well of the school system in Nagaland. Significantly more children in government schools had low E.I as compared to children studying in private schools(Table 10) . The association of E.I and A.A, was highly significant in both types of schools, confirming the strong impact of E.I and A.A regardless of where the students is studying.(Table 10). Supporting students to learn is the superordinate aim of school education. Educational organizations are picking up this

concept of EI, in hope of achieving a systemic solution to improve outcomes – academically and socially as well. Most schools aim generally for higher academic excellence in their pupils and place less importance on co-curricular or extracurricular activities.

Emotional Intelligence can be developed by schools only if the teachers and school administration provides for all round development of the children under their care. The findings from this research, in particular the focus group discussions, reveal that uniformly students, their parents and teachers all seem ignorant of the concepts and meaning of emotional intelligence. However, after explaining they all wholeheartedly accepted that it was an important part of school education as well as parental responsibility.

Many of the attributes and patterns of behaviour manifested during adolescence have a direct or indirect link to social and cultural forces operating in their environment. Even culture plays a part in the genetic endowment of an individual. In contrast to quantitative results, both Focus Group Discussions of students, their parents and teachers colourfully portray the influence of Naga culture on their emotional intelligence, their motivations and on their academic achievements.

Study on the importance of the role of counselling service in school and the relation of emotional, cognitive and social intelligence in the children has been paid little importance in Nagaland although various other research support that E.I and school counsellor contribute to the psychological wellbeing of a person. The findings of the study point out the need of an awareness of emotional intelligence in the school context and environment through the role of a school counselor, (Torrento et al 2016) stating that students' academic motivation was positively associated with school counselling utilization. They provide evidence that schools that implement social and emotional learning programs report an increase in academic success, better quality relationships between teachers and students, and a decrease in problematic behaviours. Stillman et al (2018) further affirm that this helps in experiencing feelings with clarity; recover from negative states of mind; a decisive influence on students' mental health; psychological balance in turn is related to and ultimately affects academic performance.

It is worth noting that despite the enriched curriculum with emotional literacy programs springing up in Nagaland like career guidance, life skills, substance abuse awareness, extra-curricular activities, sports week, literary day etc., students increasingly face behavioural problems, academic issues, violence and crime, decision making, emotional turmoil and lack of psychological wellbeing. Probably, school counselling and awareness of E.I may work as an antidote in the role of education and in the life of the child. It is at this point that the practice of professionally trained school counsellor is critical in helping students understand the, emotional literacy. Appropriate and timely counseling has proved beneficial in many situations (Kintner et al 2012) and may be necessary to motivate school administration to enhance emotional intelligence, both in awareness building and for providing resources.

Among the many factors that may determine the emotional development of children and youth, the role of the family must be emphasized. Indeed, the influence of

the family context in children's emotional development has been pointed out by diverse authors, whether that influence comes from what parents teach, or from the parents' own behavior. For example, Mayer and Salovey (1997) indicate that interactions within the family context mark the beginning of emotional skill acquisition, with parents teaching their children to connect their emotions with social situations that they experience. In particular, the qualitative research tools of focus group discussions and case studies were used to probe this area on the role of parents and family in developing the emotional intelligence in the children. The different FGDs debated and concluded that there are significant contributions by parents, although most confessed that they were not aware of their role in emotional intelligence of their children. Case studies supplemented the FGDs and presented both positive and negative points. Manzeske and Stright (2009) indicate, one important aspect of development during early adulthood is the use of skills to regulate both positive and negative emotions in social, educational, and professional contexts. This set of skills has received the name emotional intelligence, and has become one of the top fields attracting scientific interest in recent decades. During the interaction with the parents and in the FGD, several important clues were identified which sensitized them to emotional development such as awareness of different parenting styles, parent – child bonding, spending family time, and creating an environment for freedom of expression and feelings, encouragement and motivation.

One major point of discussion was encouragement and motivation which was felt to be lacking in the family, which majority agreed to it. One participant stated, "Of course it's not that it is not present at all but maybe we are lacking in motivation as a parent as an elder; will not praise or congratulate the child or even encourage the child.." (Parent/ male) Another participant added "motivation and encouragement, starts from the family" (parent/male). One participant further shared "I hardly get any encouragement or motivation from my relatives" (student/ male) another participant stated "We fail to encourage them and compare them with the best of the best" (parent/ male) to which one participant further stated "the parents will only compare on speak about a child who did well in their studies or achieve good things...even if our child got right in something we neglect them and start comparing with others as if what our child or others who also did well is worth nothing..." (male/parent) to which another participant shared "It will be good if the elders also try to understand us better and show or encourage us and motivate us instead of comparing us with others or being judgemental" (student/ male)

Another key point which was highlighted from the discussion was the parenting style; majority of the participants agreed that parenting style and family environment of the Nagas in general is affecting in the development of the child, to which the respondents stated; "We tend to be very authoritative" (female/parent) to which one respondent shared "I feel that my children does not express much like sharing their problems or opinions. And I feel my parenting style can be one reason because I also tend to be very strict "(male/parent). Another participant shared "for my family I am a little strict with my child and maybe it's the fault of the parents that our child does not share freely" (male/parent) another participant stated "Yes parenting and family plays a major role in E.I because majority of we Nagas do not let our children express

freely and shut them or scold them without giving them opportunity to speak listen to them” (parent/female). To which one participant shared “if my child speak, I hurriedly shut them up saying don’t say silly things ... without understanding or listening to them when they are trying to share or open up so maybe like me I am making my child hard to express their feelings or emotions or even not wanting to share it with me” (parent / male) Another participant added “less interaction in the family, friends, neighbours” (student/female).

Some of the participant however shared that the parents are understanding and encouraging; spend family time together; going for trips and family gatherings and share their difficulties and thus motivate and help each other although there are some restrictions one participant stated “family interactions and sharing their experiences helps him better in reflecting himself while answering the E.I” (student/female) another participant added “ strong family relationship is open and free with his parents and siblings, thought his parents are strict at times; the family is supportive” (male/student) another participant shared “spend family time together; parents are supportive” (female/student).

During the discussion, it was debated on how or what can the parents and family do to promote E.I among the children, to which the reports from the discussion point out that there is a need of awareness or sensitization of parenting style, encouragement and motivation should be improved; the discussion also highlighted that there is a need of spending more quality time, and that there the parents should create an environment where the child can express their emotion and feelings freely. One participant stated “should give space or create an environment for the children to share and express ... there is very less time interacting with our kids and children” (parent/ female) another participant stated “We have not given importance to E.I so this is something which is very important. And it will be very good if you could sensitize the parents as well as the teachers” (parent/male) to which another participant stated” If awareness has been given out and say I learn something about their emotions than I will be able to understand more about my child emotions” (female/parent) another participant added “there is a need for sensitization of parenting style, i think the family upbringing is really contributing the E.I of the child” (parent/male)another stated “the parents should be made aware of their parenting style, and E.I” (parent/ male).

The findings of the study is in agreement with other previous research findings for example, Gugliandolo et al (2019) where trait E.I was related to parenting style variables, and parenting practises; Elias and Weissberg(2000) also emphasized that parents should give paramount importance in developing children’s social and emotional competencies; Deshpande and Chabbria(2013)in their study likewise found a significant impact of home environment on the effect of social and emotional intelligence; George et al (2017) showed in their study that poor parenting leads to low E.I. On the other hand study by Nesrin and Mathai (2018) showed authoritative and authoritarian parenting styles show more resilience when compared to those with negligent parenting style. Kunanithaworn et al, (2018); Morris et al (2007) in their studies report motivation was correlated with perceived family support. Study results

of Soni et al (2019) further add that E.I is influenced by friends and family atmosphere. One of the aspects of parents' behavior that has great influence on children's development is parenting style (Shelto and Harol 2008), for which two important dimensions have been identified—*affect and control* (Grolnick and Gurland 2002). The first of these dimensions refers to the parents' availability and their demonstration of support and affection for their children. This set of positive practices has been related to a lower rate of externalizing problems in children, to higher self-esteem, and to good psychological adjustment (Perlman et al 2008;Manzeske and Stright 2009).

The second dimension concerning parenting styles is *control*, which is a more complex construct. According to Alegre (2011), some practices that make up this construct show positive relationships to developmental outcomes, while other practices show negative relationships or undesirable outcomes. The former would include behavior control and support for autonomy, along with inductive discipline (De Clercq et al. 2008). By contrast, practices that produce negative outcomes include most notably psychological control and harsh discipline (Shelton and Harold 2008). Despite extensive research on how parenting styles influence many aspects of the development and psychological adjustment of children and youth, little attention has been given to the relationship and influence of parenting styles on the development of emotional intelligence (Alegre 2011). According to Alegre and Benson (2010), there is evidence that the two main dimensions of parenting styles mentioned above are related to children's emotional intelligence. Namely, parental affect has proven to be positively related to children perceiving, understanding, and regulating emotions (Alegre and Benson 2007; Bennett et al. 2005). There are also data that show parental control to be related to children perceiving, understanding, and regulating emotions (Morris et al. 2007; Pears and Moses 2003; Perlman et al. 2008). However, as indicated above, the construct of parental control is quite complex and includes a number of practices with different outcomes that need to be analyzed.

It is true that low emotional intelligence alone is not responsible for low academic performance in Nagaland, but certain other factors such as, social economic status, job prospects conditions of school, availability of teachers, resources etc. However, a high EI could transcend many of these obstacles as discussed earlier. This research has provided substantial data on the role of parents and family in the development of E.I; and suggests that there is an urgent need of sensitization of parenting style, home environment, motivation and awareness of E.I and its relation to the development of a child social behaviour and psychological and emotional development. Clearly the research on parenting style and emotional intelligence is still very limited in Nagaland. Exploring in depth the effects of different parenting style is needed. Future research could be more interventional , longitudinal cohort studies on the different parenting styles and its effect on or contribution to emotional intelligence will add significantly to our knowledge.

Limitations of this research would include inability to collect more detailed information on academic performances, participation in co-curricular and extracurricular activities, parental styles and imputation of Morung into child development. Perhaps a more intensive sociocultural study, based on actual practices

would provide a more stronger evidence of how Naga culture enhances emotional intelligence. Future research should be more action-oriented and evaluate specific interventions such as school counselling at various stages of high school and university level education. An inter-state multicentric study in the northeastern region on similar lines of the present research will certainly benefit policy makers and educational authorities in practically integrating emotional intelligence training in existing curricula without adversely affecting other objectives.

Conclusion

Emotional Intelligence significantly impacts Academic Achievement, despite low levels of academic performance and low levels of emotional intelligence. In general, there was a lack of awareness on emotional intelligence and its components, but after enlightening, all stakeholders, students, teachers and parents, unanimously agreed on its importance and the need to enhance it through a suitable counselling course for high school students to increase their emotional intelligence

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